

FABACEAE FAMILY IN FLORA IN THE FERGANA VALLEY, RARE SPECIES OF ASTRAGALUS

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INTRODUCTION

The distribution zones of the species listed in the Red Book are 23 zones in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Rare plants are found in all highlands of Central Asia (hills, deserts, pastures, and mountains). They are especially numerous and densely distributed in the mountainous areas, and in Uzbekistan, such mountain zones are the ridges that make up the Fergana Valley. In other words, the Western Tianshan and Pamir Alay mountain ranges are areas where cannabis is abundant. In addition, all the mountains can form a range of unique species. In particular, 68 species have been found in the Gissar Mountains, 27 in the Pamir Alay Range, 27 in the Kyzylkum Desert, 33 in the Chatkal Mountains, 25 in the Nurata Mountains, 10 in the Bobotag Mountains, and more than 10 in the Piskom-Ugam Mountains. [2.Pratov and p. 2011].

Astragalus rubellus, ie red astragalus, is not found in the Fergana Valley, except in the Yazyavan desert (Kokand sands and the village of Karakalpakstan). [1."Red Book". 2016].

ABSTRACT

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the rarity of Fabaceae is very high, with a large share of Astragalus species. This group of species is endemic in terms of distribution, most of which are distributed within the Fergana Valley. This article is about the rare species of Astragalus that are found in the Fergana Valley.

Main part. 35 Uzbekistan/6 Fergana valley

1. Boris Astragali - Астргал Бориса - Astragalus Borissianus,

2. Zarxal Astragal - Астргал Позолоченный - Astragalus Auratus,

3. Ikkirang Astragal - Астргал двухцветкововидных - Astragalus dianthoides

4. Yulingan Astragal - Астргал оборвонный - Astragalus rhacodes

5. Qizg'ish Astragal - Астргал Красновeтый - Astragalus rubellus

6. Janubiy Farg'ona Astragali - Астргал Южноферганский - Astragalus austroferganicus

Astragalus Borissianus. Rare endemic of the Alai Range. Short description. Perennial, almost stem plant, 30 cm high, with short mi, strongly shortened stems, dressed old leaf stalks. Leaves long 10-23 cm, leaves 10-13-pair, oblong elliptical or lanceolate, pointed, long 7-15 mm, hard, pressed-white on both sides hairy.

Brushes-compressed, short, 6-8-color movie. The beans are sessile, oblong-ovate, 14-15 mm long, rigid-

protruding-white natty, two-celled. Blooms in June bears fruit in August. Spread. Fergana region: Alai- ridge: Shakhimardan river basin. Habitat. Rocky slopes among juniper trees. Number. It is found by single specimens. Reproduction. Seed. The reasons for the change in the number and area Not installed. Cultivation. No information is available. Security measures. Special security measures are not developed [3.plantarium.1."Red Book".2016].

Astragalus Auratus. Rare, endemic species of the Alay and Turkestan ranges. It is spread at the Alay range: nearby the Shakhimardan, the Kul-Kubbon, the Jordan, the Uvlardisai, the Sokh, the Peshkaut valleys at the altitude of 1600-1800 m (the Ferghana region). Inhabits dry stony slopes, pebbles, rarely mounds. The quantity is unknown. Limiting factors: grazing. Measures of protection: not protected. Short description. Perennial, almost herbaceous stem up to 15 cm. The lower leaves are simple, single, the upper leaves are biparous, obovate, on both sides appressed hairy. Peduncles almost equal to leaves, 6-8-flowered, bright yellow flowers. It blooms and bears fruit in July.

Astragalus dianthoides. Rare endemic species of the Alay range. It is spread at the Alay range: nearby the villages Chimion, Shakhimardan, Sadkak, Kadamzhai, Akpilal, Vuadil, Sokh (the Ferghana region). Inhabits grey soils, conglomerates and shales, ravines in foothills. Rare, isolated specimens can be found. Measures of protection: not protected. Short description. Perennial, almost stemless plant 3-4 cm high, densely appressed-pubescent. Leaves 1-2 cm long with thin petioles up to 2-5 mm long. Leaflets are 4-5-paired, oblong, 2-7 mm long, wide about 1 mm, densely haired on both sides. Brushes with 2-3 flowers. Calyx tubular, length 12-16 mm. Corolla yellow, sometimes reddening. Pods 20-25 mm long, 3 mm wide, tapered to the base and apex, with a very short spout,

transversely veined, laterally compressed, finely appressed hairy. Blossoms in April; bears fruit in April-May.

Astragalus rhacodes. A rare species of the Alai Range. Short description. The semi-shrub is woody in the lower part. Leaves 7-12 cm long, petioles 15-17 cm long, whitish. Flowers are equal to leaves, sometimes longer than them. Clusters are loose, 10-25 flowers. The calyx swells with plots. The flowers are yellow. Pods are semi-oval or oblong-semi-oval. Blossoms in May-June, bears fruit in June-July. Rare endemic species of the Alay range. It is spread at the Alay range: nearby the villages Shakhimardan Sadkak and Kiziltag (the Ferghana region). Inhabits red sands, stony and earth- slopes at the altitude of 1200-1600 m. The quantity is unknown. Limiting factors: pasturing. Measures of protection: not protected.

Astragalus rubellus. Extremely rare, endemic species of the Ferghana valley. spread at the Ferghana valley, nearby Kokand, the village Kara - Kalpak

and the Yazyayan sands (the Ferghana region). Inhabits sandy hills and slightly saline sands. The quantity is unknown. Limiting factors: decreasing of sandy area. Measures of protection: not protected. Extremely rare endemic to the Ferghana Valley. Brief description. Perennial stemless herb up to 35 cm high. The stem is white-haired. Leaves up to 30-35 cm long, protruding - wormy, leaves 14-18 - paired, rounded. Peduncles 15 cm long, short - protruding - pubescent. Clusters 11-18 cm long, consist of 8-15 flowers. The flowers are red. Pods up to 2 cm long, inflated, ovoid leathery, with protruding seams. It blooms in April-May, bears fruit in May-June.

Astragalus austroferganicus. Endemic of the foothills of the Northern Pamir - Alai. Short description. Perennial 10-20 cm in height. Stems are thin, whitish. Leaves 1-2-3 are paired, 1-2-6 cm long, rounded leaves. Calyx 12-18 mm long, white and black scattered hairy. Flag yellow 20 mm long, wings 17-18 mm long,

boat 18-20 mm long. Pods are 20-50 mm long, with a pedicle 2-3 mm long, straight with a spout 8-10 mm long, whitish-gray. Blossoms in May; bears fruit in June. Spread . Fergana Valley: Fergana region (Yangiariq). Habitat. Salty clays. Number. Collected once by A. Joffe in 1928. The species apparently disappeared. Reproduction Seed. Causes of Rare endemic species of the Ferghana valley. It is spread at the foothills, nearby Ferghana city (the Ferghana region). Inhabits salty clays. The plants were collected by A. Joffe in 1928. Probably disappeared. Limiting factors: pasturing. Measure s of protection: not protected.[Vinogradova]

CONCLUSION

At present, there is no complete information about any of the plants included in the Red Data Book of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In addition, the book lists the species in a specific category and provides protection measures for that

category. However, in conclusion, despite the fact that the plants are divided into this category, no specific protection measures have been developed.

1. In danger of extinction, requiring special protection to survive.

2. The range was small and unique, disappearing rapidly and requiring strict control.

3. Over a period of time, the number and area are shrinking due to natural or anthropological factors.

Looking at this table, more endemic species of *Astragalus* are found in this area. And in fact, they are the only species that need strict protection. The fact that *Astragalus austroferganicus* is not included in any network is analytical evidence of the lack of data on the species.

References:

1. Red book(1) in the Uzbekistan 2016
2. Pratorov.O', Madumarov.T.,Naraliyeva.N. Rare plants in the Uzbekistan
3. Red book(1) in the Uzbekistan. 2006, 1988
4. Vinogradova RM Section Aureophora of the genus *Astragalus* II Keys to plants of Central Asia. T. 6. Tashkent: Fan, 1981. - S. 212-213.
5. Vinogradova RM Section Lertory of the genus *Astragalus* II Keys to Plants of Central Asia. T. 6. Tashkent: Fan, 1981. - P. 274.
6. Vinogradova RM Section Xiphidium of the genus *Astragalus* Keys to plants of Central Asia. T.6. Tashkent: Fan, 1981.-- S. 185-188.
7. Goloskokov V. P. Sem. Santalaceae // Flora of Kazakhstan. T. 4. Alma - Ata: AN KazSSR, 1960. - S. 83-88
8. Goncharov NF New species of the genus *Astragalus* Bot. mat. Emblem . in - that bot. Academy of Sciences of the USSR. T. 7.L. 1938 145.
9. Goncharov NF New astragals and sharp boats // Bot. mat. Emblem . in - that bot. Academy of Sciences of the USSR. Vol. 1.L., 1941.-- S. 85-105.
10. Goncharov NF New and critical astragals // Bot. mat. Coat of arms, in - that bot. Academy of Sciences of the USSR. T. 9. Issue 4.L. , 1946.-- S. 113-151.
11. Goncharov NF Section *Astenolobium* of the genus *Astragalus* / Flora of the USSR. T.